

The Contribution of Tourism to the Economic Growth of a Country

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ABSTRACT: Tourism has economic effects as well as political and social effects, but its economic effects are more than social and political effects. Tourism is closely related to the economic growth and development of countries and creates better job opportunities and an increase in income. Therefore, tourism is a significant cause of economic development, the economic value of which increases with each passing day. It can make a positive change in the economic and social situation of the countries. The results of the research indicate that, along with increasing the income of developing countries, the development of tourism has also created suitable activities, and while reducing the level of poverty, it has prevented the immigration of young people and attracted foreign investment. The findings of the research show that one out of every nine working people in the world is engaged in tourism-related matters.

KEY WORDS: Economy, tourism and development.

INTRODUCTION

Tourism is an old term, which was used officially as tourism and tourist for the first time by the United Nations Organization in 1937, but the front of this industry going back to history years ago, England was the first country among the European countries to start the tourism industry and with the industrialization of Western countries. This culture became a tradition among people and finally with the invention of iron lines. Tourism has become an international industry and its economic value has become evident. Accordingly, the industry for the first time spread out in Europe and then in other continents. At present, the attention of most businessmen and opinion holders have returned to the tourism industry, even though most of the countries of the world consider the budget of this industry before the defense budget. Currently, the tourism industry is growing and developing so, according to the reports of the International Tourism Organization, this industry had a growth rate of 2.8 percent in 2012, which is higher than the growth rate of the global economy which was estimated at 2.5 percent, was a loss, this growth show that tourism has directly generated two trillion dollars in revenue and around 100.3 million direct jobs, and on the economic growth and development of the country had a clear effect.

Research Objectives

- i) to increase the economic impact of tourism
- ii) to clarify the value of tourism

Research Questions

- i) What are the economic effects of tourism development?
- ii) What is the value of tourism?

Economic effects of tourism

Tourism is the largest service industry in terms of revenue in the world, the growth and development of which creates economic, political, social and environmental effects and leads to the creation of various types of engagements. It can directly affect the production, trade and services, transportation, hotel management. Therefore, most of the countries of the world are competitively enjoying the economic, social, political and cultural aspects of tourism. They use it to get employment and income. Presently, tourism has developed more in the world and most countries have succeeded in improving their situation through tourism and solving their economic problems -lack of income and unemployment on the rise) Zaruni, 1396 .P :1 (On this basis, tourism is a

system that has a wide relationship with economic growth and, along with the increase in income, it also generates appropriate activities and is of great value for economic growth and development, that is why economists call it exports (Arab, 1393 P :60).

Tourism is an ancient activity; which humans have started doing and it existed in different forms at different times .It plays an effective role in tourism and is the best economic activity during the growth .Currently, most of the countries of the world receive more than 10 percent of their gross domestic income from tourism .Based on international tourism statistics, in 2015, the income from international tourism accounted for 30 percent of the gross income of most countries, and in 2017, the number of international tourists exceeded 1.3 billion people. The revenue reached 1/23 trillion dollars, which had a clear impact on the economy of the countries (Ghorbani and colleagues, 1400, P :543).

It is a phenomenon that, in the case of the right program, can increase productivity, raise the standard of living, create general well-being and more engagements .Economists refer to the tourism industry as an industry that generates investment and employment, and they pay attention to it, and they believe that the development of tourism leads to an increase in the economic value of money, if a country uses its capabilities and opportunities .take advantage and make the wheel of this industry move in their country, they will face great economic growth and change (Shakuri, 1396 .P :34).

Some of the economic effects of the terrorism industry will be shown below:

1 .Increase of incomes: Based on the figures published by the) United Nations Tourism Organization(in 1950 the income of all countries was higher than 2.1 billion dollars which number was 856 billion dollars in 2007 and 2010 this number reached one trillion dollars)Shakuri, 1396, P :34 .(Similarly, based on the annual report of the United Nations World Tourism Organization, 983 million tourists traveled around the world in 2011, while the number of tourists in 2010 was 940 reached millions of people, which is a growth of 6/4 percent compared to last year.

In this series, in 2010, the revenue received from this route was 928 billion US dollars, while in 2011, it registered a new record and this number increased to 1030 billion dollars .According to the prediction of this organization, in the year 2030, the number of tourists will reach 8/1 billion people)Tourism Highlights, 2012 Edition .P .2). Therefore, it can be said that tourism is the main part of the global economy .t has the potential to create economic growth at the international level, thus it plays a fundamental role in reducing the level of poverty in the developing countries .The development of tourism leads to an increase in the income of the people and helps to increase the production of national income and creates direct and indirect engagements and leads to an increase in the government's income (Shafi, 1393, P :78).

Based on the reports of the International Tourism Organization, the number of tourists in 2017, which was accompanied by a growth of 6 percent, reached 1.4 billion people .One billion and 323 million tourism trips were made and the total revenue of this industry reached 1.23 trillion dollars .According to the International Council of Tourism, in which 185 countries from 25 regions were investigated, In this series, in 2018, the share of tourism was 10.4 percent, which I had in the gross domestic product of the world .The tool has been created and it is estimated that in the year 2020, the number of international travelers will increase to 1.6 billion people and their income will increase to two thousand billion dollars .In this regard, in 2018, the total number of migrants to Europe was 713 million and to America was 217 million, but in contrast, the number of migrants to African and Middle Eastern developing countries . There were 67 million people and through this way they brought more revenue(Fitras, 1398, P :3)

2 .Increasing the level of engagement :One of the obvious characteristics of tourism is its impact on engagement, which plays an important role in creating job opportunities and engages most people in simple tasks that do not require any expertise, in some parts of the world .In developing countries, more than 50 percent of active people are engaged in activities that are directly and indirectly related to tourism, but in some countries where the development of tourism is unrestricted, that is why tourism People engaged in related activities make up 5 percent of the population)Bakhtiari, 1389, P :54 .(Despite the fact that the primary purpose of tourism development is not to create engagement, but its development creates such a system, which has a high degree of engagement and ability, currently tourism is a source of engagement.

It is a big industry for production and it can make a fundamental change in the employment situation of the developing countries .In 1992, one out of every 15 working people was engaged in tourism, and in the same year, the total number of working people in this sector reached 130 million people, which is 6.6 percent of the working people of all sectors .This number was around 10-10 percent from 150 million people in 2005 and increased to 11 percent in 2008)World Tourism Organization, 2009 (based on research. With the arrival of 20 nomads to an area, one job is created directly and one job is created for every six nomads directly and indirectly (Arab, 1393, P :61).

Therefore, Zivas and his friends They believe that tourism is considered the best refuge for workers from other industries and the tourism industry has diverted most of the workers from other industries to this industry and adds that the occupation of this industry is very attractive and accessible for people .It is possible (Srivas,1999 (as well as (Sharini), at the end of a study, has come to the conclusion that tourism is an important source of income for the rural community, therefore, the activities that tourism It is related, such as providing a room for travelers, food preparation, hand-selling, transportation and other new activities that can be created through tourism (Sharili, 1380, 41)

Therefore, tourism is the largest industry in the world, which creates many employment and competitive opportunities, while in the last decade, the growth rate of this industry in the United States of America was twice as bad as that of other industries .)Chales, R .2003, P :86 .(On this basis, tourism is an important source of employment in different regions of the world, and one out of every nine workers worldwide is engaged in the tourism industry, and this is the most important It is a foundation and organization, which has engaged a lot of human power, (Sharili, 1382, P:26).

According to the report of the International Organization of Tourism, the tourism industry in 2012 is about 100.3 million directly .have created jobs .One out of every 12 jobs in the world is related to tourism .Based on this, the growth of the tourism industry is estimated at 4 percent until 2022, which can create 328 million jobs .Based on this, the tourism industry contributed \$6.3 trillion to GDP in 2011, creating 255 million jobs and \$743 billion in direct and indirect investment (Tourism and International Travel Council, 2012).

3 .Lower unemployment rate: The tourism industry has the best effect on the lower unemployment rate, increasing the income level, providing energy resources and the handicraft market, currently in the literature of the economic development of a country.

The important issues are employment and unemployment, because employment and employment are an important source of income for people and an important reason for the eradication of poverty in society .The increase in unemployment is an important reason for the decline in economic growth and the emergence of social and political conflicts .

Therefore, tourism is an industry that employs people with different skills and ages and is an important way to overcome unemployment .Therefore, tourism creates permanent, seasonal and part-time employment for manpower in various places .and has contributed to the level of unemployment, tourism in the region, apart from direct engagement, other activities that are related to it, such as construction works, rent, handicrafts and other such indirect engagements are also created)Nasirizadeh and Others, 1382, p :211 .(Unemployment is an important economic and social issue in human societies, which most countries in the world, especially third world countries, are facing .The only way to create job opportunities to reduce is to expand the tourism industry (Mirzai, 1389, P :6).

4 .Lower level of immigration :The results of the research indicate that the development of tourism prevents the immigration of young people by creating job opportunities and strengthens the sense of connection between people with their place of residence and strengthens their national motivation .Along with this, tourism increases the ability of young people in the administration and management of rural settlements)Kurdwani, 1398, P :223 .(On this basis, Ghulam Sarizdi and his friends believe that tourism creates a fair distribution of income in rural areas, which itself prevents immigration to the big cities and helps the development and attractiveness of villages (Sardizi, 2012, P :17).

Also, tourism is an important factor in stimulating the growth of society's production and creating job opportunities for young people, which prevents the immigration of young people, leads to the protection of productive capacity in the region, eliminates poverty and economic development .It is considered the best way to solve the problems)Qadiri et al., 1389, P :107), tourism can stop the evacuation of the shelters in rural areas and reduce the level of immigration of the rural community .It helps in creating, increasing the level of income, diversifying economic activities, strengthening social relations, preserving cultural heritage and the natural environment, and preventing indiscriminate immigration in rural areas (Iftikhari, 1381, P : 27-33.)

5: The height of the purchasing power of people: a region with the development of tourism? New money comes to the economy and strengthens the regional economy and can create diversity in the regional economy and strengthen people's purchasing power . The development of tourism stimulates the regional economy and increases per capita income at the regional level (Zaruni, 1396, P:3).

In the same way, tourism is an economic activity, which is exchanged annually in billions of dollars and plays an important role in the economic development of different regions, which creates social and cultural effects along with economic effects and the distribution of income .Roads provide employment and eliminate poverty .On this basis, Qurbani and his colleagues have come to

the conclusion during a research that, with the development of tourism, they find market and sales centers, create new markets and develop People strengthen their purchasing power)Ghorbani and colleagues, 1400, P :543 .(besides, the development of tourism leads to the increase in the prices of land and goods in tourist areas .Research shows that in the areas where the tourism industry is undergoing growth and development, the prices of land and goods in these areas have increased compared to before (Shafi'i, 2013, P :80).

6: Increase in foreign investment: Tourism leads to the promotion of investment and opens up opportunities for foreign investment .A research in Iran found that tourism has played an effective role in the development of employment, the increase in investment, the increase in income and the quality of life)Bazazan, 1399, P :64 .(The development of tourism leads to the economic growth of the host country, and every monetary unit that is injected into the economic cycle of the host country with the arrival of tourists, leads to production and creates economic growth.

CONCLUSION

At the end of the above discussion, we can summarize that tourism has more economic effects than political and social effects .Tourism is considered to be an important source of income for the developed and developing countries of the world and the main reason for the creation of job opportunities, which, along with the increase in income, also creates appropriate activities. Therefore, economists have decided to invest in the tourism industry .He mentions employment as a productive industry and pays attention to it .Research findings indicate that tourism has played an effective role in increasing the income of developing countries and creating job opportunities, and every nine people in the world has a job .One of the gurus in the tourism industry is busy working in, hence, the development of tourism stimulates the local economy and increases the income per person.

Likewise, the results of the research are good, that the development of tourism creates better job opportunities for the youth by creating engagements and increasing the level of income, and prevents illegal immigration in rural areas and diversification of economic activities . In this way, tourism can provide the basis for foreign investment towards developing countries and thus inject new money into the economy of the host country.

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Conflict of Interest

No potential conflict of interest was reported by the authors.

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